

Breast Cancer Sub-typing using Digital Mammograms and Machine Learning: Predicting Invasiveness and Tumor Grade

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Abstract—Despite significant advancements, Breast Cancer (BC) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among women worldwide. Effective management and prognosis of BC depend on accurate assessment of tumor invasiveness and histological grade. Traditionally, conclusive classification relies on biopsy and histopathology, which are invasive and can introduce diagnostic delays. This study presents a Machine Learning (ML) approach for automatic detection and sub-typing of BC, using digital mammograms, epidemiological, and medical history data. The goal is to effectively classify BC as *in situ* vs. invasive, and characterize the tumor grade (grade 2 vs. grade 3). The proposed methodology involves two main steps: (1) detection of Regions of Interest (ROIs), and (2) classification of the ROIs using a feature-based ML methodology. A new dataset was collected specifically for this study, consisting of images from 58 patients, along with annotated ground truth images from two expert radiologists. Image-derived features were combined with epidemiological and medical history features, and multiple feature selection and classification schemes were evaluated to identify the best models. The proposed approach achieved 91.9% sensitivity, 83.6% specificity, 88.3% accuracy, and an AUC of 0.88 for *in situ* vs. invasive classification. For tumor grading (grade 2 vs. 3), it achieved 82.5% sensitivity, 85.7% specificity, 84.4% accuracy, and an AUC of 0.84. By reducing reliance on invasive biopsy for initial sub-typing, this method offers a faster, non-invasive, and accurate tool to support BC diagnosis. Its translation into clinical workflows has the potential to improve diagnostic efficiency and treatment planning, as well as enhance patient outcomes.

Index Terms— Breast cancer, Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD), Machine Learning, Sub-typing

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast Cancer (BC) remains a significant global health concern. The International Agency for Research on Cancer projects that by 2030, there will be 2.7 million new BC cases and 800,000 BC-related deaths globally [1]. BC can be classified as *in situ* or invasive, depending on whether the cancer has spread beyond its original boundaries. While *in situ* carcinomas are confined to the ducts or lobules of the breast, invasive carcinomas extend beyond their site of origin, infiltrating surrounding tissue [2], [3]. Accurate classification is crucial, as invasive BC typically requires more aggressive management strategies [4]. Another essential parameter in BC prognosis and treatment planning is tumor grade. Tumor

grading assesses the aggressiveness of cancer cells by examining their morphology and proliferation rates under a microscope. Tumors are typically assigned a grade from 1 to 3 [5], with higher grades indicating more aggressive cancers [6]. High-grade tumors are associated with poorer prognosis and a higher risk of metastasis [7].

Currently, the standard practice for determining invasiveness status and tumor grade involves performing a biopsy followed by detailed histopathological analysis [8]. However, this process has important limitations. It introduces substantial delays in obtaining the results, during which patients may be lost to follow-up. The American Cancer Society (ACS) reports a 5-year relative survival rate of 99% for localized BC, dropping to 86% for regional spread, and further to 31% for distant metastases [6]. Thus, delays can lead to narrowing the window for effective treatment, especially in cases where early start of therapy is important [5]. Furthermore, biopsies impose financial burdens on healthcare systems, with false positive breast biopsies alone estimated to cost more than \$2 billion annually in the United States [9]. Developing reliable, accurate, and non-invasive methods to classify and grade BC could alleviate some of these limitations.

Mammography is an effective, non-invasive screening modality for BC diagnosis and, eventually, management. Over the years, various Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems have been proposed for the classification between benign and malignant breast abnormalities using mammographic images, Machine Learning (ML), or Deep Learning (DL) techniques [10], [11]. Despite these advances, only one work has focused on the use of mammograms for the classification of BC invasiveness. Specifically, Vy et al., 2022, developed an ML algorithm using XGBoost to distinguish Ductal Carcinoma In Situ (DCIS) from minimally invasive BC in a cohort of 420 patients, achieving an accuracy of 84% [12]. The study extracted radiomic features from mammograms and demonstrated the potential of ML to assist radiologists in identifying cancer invasiveness, which is critical for treatment planning. Most approaches to tumor grading rely on histopathological images [13]. Only one study by Alaeikhanehshir et al., 2024, extended this approach by applying a DL model (U-Net) to mammographic images to discriminate between low- and high-risk DCIS [14]. The model achieved an AUC of 0.76, supporting the potential use of DL in mammography for tumor grading. These studies have shown promising but modest results and focused on small patient populations or restricted classification tasks. Despite this progress, existing

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Fig. 1. Diagram of the proposed methodology.

studies achieve only moderate performance, and usually address only one specific biological challenge at a time, rather than providing an integrated classification of subtype, invasiveness, and grade simultaneously.

In this study, an algorithm is proposed for the automatic classification of breast lesions as *in situ* vs. invasive and for tumor grading as grade 2 vs. grade 3, using digital mammograms, epidemiological and medical history information, along with feature-based ML. The methodology consists of two main steps: (1) detection of Regions of Interest (ROIs) and (2) classification of ROIs using a feature-based ML pipeline. The algorithm was developed and validated on a new dataset including data from 58 patients. Ninety-six image features were extracted and combined with 12 epidemiological and medical history features. They were ranked using 8 different feature selection algorithms. Ten classifiers were evaluated to effectively characterize the invasiveness and grade of each abnormality. The proposed methodology, outlined in Figure 1, achieved 88.3% and 84.4% accuracy, respectively.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Design and Data Collection

A dataset was created specifically for this study to overcome the limitations of publicly available mammography databases, which often lack detailed annotations, biopsy confirmations, or contain outdated or scanned images. The dataset includes precise annotations of individual abnormalities, confirmed by histopathology, serving as the ground truth. Full-field digital mammograms were obtained from screenings conducted between 2022 and 2023, from different local healthcare facilities, including the Cyprus Population Screening Program in Aglantzia and Linopetra, Limassol, and Nicosia General Hospitals. The population included women 38 to 80 years of age (Table I). From each participant, two mammographic views were collected—Cranio-Caudal (CC) and Medio-Lateral Oblique (MLO)—resulting in a total of 116 images from 58 patients (Fig. 2). Epidemiological and medical history information was also collected for each participant. Ethical considerations were addressed, and the study received approval from

TABLE I
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE POPULATION SELECTED FOR THE STUDY

Variable	Malignant Population ($n = 58$)
Patient Age	
<i>Mean \pm STD</i>	65.2 \pm 9
<i>Median</i>	66
<i>Range</i>	38 - 80
<i>Interquartile Range</i>	59 - 73
BI-RADS breast density	
<i>a</i>	18
<i>b</i>	20
<i>c</i>	18
<i>d</i>	2
Invasiveness	
<i>In situ</i>	16
<i>Invasive</i>	42
Tumor Grading	
<i>Grade 1</i>	0
<i>Grade 2</i>	39
<i>Grade 3</i>	19

STD: standard deviation

the Institutional Review Board (Cyprus National Bioethics Committee). Informed consent forms were collected during the most recent screening round. This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

The dataset reflects real-world variability in breast imaging and includes diverse abnormality types such as Micro-Calcifications (MCs), masses, architectural distortions, and asymmetry. Two clinicians (C.N., radiologist with 27 years of experience, and A.Y., consultant breast surgeon with 10 years of experience) identified the eligible patients. Two radiologists (G.Sk. with 6 years of experience and E.O.V. with 5 years of experience), annotated all images. Suspicious cases were further investigated with

Fig. 2. Example images. Case 1 (top row): Mammographic views of a 68-year-old woman with grade 2 invasive breast cancer and BI-RADS breast density category *a*. Case 2 (bottom row): Mammographic views of a 66-year-old woman with grade 3 *in situ* breast cancer and BI-RADS breast density category *c*. For each case: (A) Most recent mammogram in MLO view with precise annotation of a biopsy-confirmed malignancy. (B) Most recent mammogram in CC view with precise annotations of a biopsy-confirmed malignancy. All images were annotated by two expert radiologists.

biopsy and histopathological analysis to provide definitive classification of tumor type and grade. Among the 58 cases, 16 were diagnosed as *in situ* BC and 42 as invasive BC. Tumor grading identified 39 cases as grade 2 and 19 as grade 3. This distribution reflects typical clinical presentation patterns, where grade 1 tumors are rarely detected at screening.

B. Segmentation of Regions of Interest (ROIs)

Pre-processing of the mammograms (Fig. 3) included the following steps: (i) normalization to adjust pixel intensity values, (ii) Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [15], and (iii) gamma correction [16]. Normalization was performed to rescale the pixel intensity values of each mammogram to a standard range. This step reduces inter-image variability due to differences in acquisition settings or equipment, ensuring that subsequent processing and analysis are not biased by absolute intensity differences. Normalization is important in medical imaging, as it helps standardize the input image data, improving model robustness and convergence during training. CLAHE was applied using tiles to improve local contrast, particularly within dense breast regions. It operates by dividing the

image into small non-overlapping regions (tiles) and applying histogram equalization to each, with a contrast limiting step to prevent noise amplification. This method enhances the visibility of subtle features such as MCs, which might otherwise be obscured in dense breasts. The tile size was chosen with trial and error to balance between enhancing local contrast and avoiding over-amplification of noise or artifacts. Gamma correction was performed with a gamma value of 2 to remap pixel intensities and improve overall visualization. Gamma correction is a non-linear operation that adjusts the luminance of the image. It compresses the higher intensity values and expands the lower ones, making faint structures more visible and improving the quality of the image. This is especially useful in mammography, where subtle differences in tissue density are diagnostically important.

Segmentation was performed to isolate ROIs for further analysis. This process included: (i) thresholding, (ii) application of morphological operations, and (iii) removal of periphery pixels. Thresholding converted images to binary, eliminating low-intensity regions typically corresponding to normal tissue. Threshold values were optimized during training via histogram analysis to maximize the global classification rate. Morphological operations included erosion (2-pixel radius) in order to remove isolated noise and small artifacts, followed by closing (10-pixel radius) to consolidate connected structures. Finally, high-intensity regions along the periphery, typically corresponding to skin or artifacts, were excluded to avoid false detections. The remaining areas were considered as ROIs for subsequent analysis.

C. Feature Extraction and Selection

Various image features were extracted from each ROI and combined with epidemiological and medical history data to improve classification. Each ROI yielded 96 image features, including shape, intensity-based, First-Order Statistics (FOS), and texture features computed using the Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). GLCM features were computed at 0° , 45° , 90° , and 135° , with the mean and standard deviation calculated for each direction and for offset distances $D_1 = 5$, $D_2 = 15$, and $D_3 = 25$ pixels, producing 24 values per distance. Personal medical history was encoded as 0 (negative), 1 (other diseases except cancer), 2 (other cancers), or 3 (BC). Family medical history was encoded as 0 (negative), 1 (other cancers), or 2 (BC). The final feature vector for each ROI contained 108 values, representing 108 features.

To reduce dimensionality and improve classification performance, redundant features were excluded using multiple feature selection methods: (i) t-test, (ii) Maximum Relevance–Minimum Redundancy (MRMR), (iii) Feature Importance using Extra Trees (FI-ET), (iv) Random Forest (FI-RF), (v) XGBoost (FI-XGB), (vi) SelectKBest, (vii) Sequential Forward Selection (SFS), and (viii) Sequential Backward Selection (SBS). Methods (i)–(vi) produced ranked scores, retaining the top 20 features for further

Fig. 3. Effect of the pre-processing in a 66-year-old woman with grade 3 *in situ* breast cancer and BI-RADS breast density category *c*. (A) Original most recent MLO image. (B) Zoomed region marked by the red square in A showing an area with a malignancy (indicated by the arrow). (C) Zoomed region marked by the green square in A, showing an area without suspicious regions. (D) Image after CLAHE. (E) Final pre-processed image after Gamma correction. (F) Zoomed region marked by the red square in E, showing the same area as B, after pre-processing. (G) Zoomed region marked by the green square in E, showing the same area as C, after pre-processing.

evaluation. SFS and SBS were then applied to identify the subsets with the best classification performance. A majority-rule approach was used to retain features selected by at least four techniques. Given the two distinct classification tasks, separate feature selection processes were conducted for each task (Table II and Table III).

As is common in clinical practice, the dataset was imbalanced. To address this, the Adaptive Synthetic Sampling Approach for Imbalanced Learning (ADASYN) [17] was applied during training to generate synthetic examples for the minority class. The test set was not augmented. ADASYN adaptively creates more synthetic data points for minority class samples that are harder to learn, thereby balancing class distributions and enhancing model robustness. This approach not only equalizes class sizes but also focuses learning on challenging cases, potentially improving the classifier’s performance on underrepresented outcomes. Both standardization and normalization were applied to the feature data before model training and evaluation. These processing steps are essential for ensuring that features are compared equally, particularly when combining features with different scales or distributions.

D. Training and Comparison of Classifier Designs

Two separate binary classification tasks were addressed: (i) classification of *in situ* vs. invasive BC, and (ii) grading of tumors as grade 2 vs. grade 3. Nine classifiers were evaluated: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naive Bayes (NB), Decision Trees (DT), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), AdaBoost (ADA), Bagging (Bag), and Ensemble Voting. For k-NN, neighbor values of 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11 were compared to select the optimal setting. SVM was tested with linear, polynomial, and Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernels. Ensemble Voting included both hard and soft voting strategies. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) with varying architectures were optimized based on validation loss and

accuracy.

Classifiers were trained and validated using Leave-One-Patient-Out (LOPO) Cross-Validation (CV), ensuring that data from a patient appears in either the training or test set, to ensure robust generalization. Classification performance was evaluated using sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and the Area Under the receiver operating characteristic Curve (AUC).

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Initially, the extracted features were used to identify the true abnormalities and eliminate falsely detected ROIs. Using LDA in a LOPO CV scheme, an accuracy of 84% with 0.82 AUC was achieved.

For the classification of *in situ* vs. invasive BC, 13 features were selected (Table II). LDA was built with a linear discriminant criterion and no prior probabilities, k-NN with $k = 11$, SVM with a linear kernel, and Ensemble Voting combining LDA, SVM (linear kernel), and MLP in a hard voting scheme. The sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy across LOPO CV ranged from 77–92%, 61–84%, and 72–88%, respectively (Fig. 4). The highest and most consistent performance was achieved using an ANN, which reached 91.9% sensitivity, 83.6% specificity, 88.3% accuracy, and an AUC of 0.88. The ANN model had one hidden layer with 56 neurons and approximately 2,400 trainable parameters. Batch normalization, adaptive dropout regularization (0.1), and Gaussian noise (0.1) were employed for regularization. The model was trained with the Adam optimizer (learning rate 1×10^{-4} , batch size 128) for 100 epochs.

For tumor grading (grade 2 vs. grade 3), 13 features were selected (Table III). The sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy in LOPO CV ranged between 24–82%, 52–86%, and 42–84%, respectively (Fig. 4). LDA and k-NN retained the same configurations, while in SVM an RBF kernel was used. Ensemble Voting combined k-NN ($k = 11$), SVM

TABLE II

FEATURE RANKINGS FOR *in situ* VS. INVASIVE BC CLASSIFICATION USING VARIOUS SELECTION TECHNIQUES, WITH THE FINAL SELECTION HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD.

t-test	MRMR	FI-ET	FI-RF	FI-XGB	SelectKBest	SFS	SBS
Cont. 0 D1 ¹	Eccentricity	Euler Number	ED	Area	MaAL ⁶	Eccentricity	MiAL ⁷
Cont. 45 D1	Euler Number	Cont. 0 D1	Perimeter	Perimeter	Cont. 0 D1	Orientation	Eccentricity
Cont. 90 D1	ED ³	Cont. 45 D1	Cont. 0 D1	Max Intensity	Cont. 45 D1	Min Intensity	Orientation
Cont. 135 D1	Solidity	Cont. 90 D1	Cont. 45 D1	Cont. 0 D1	Cont. 90 D1	Max Intensity	Solidity
Cont. Mean D1	Perimeter	Cont. Mean D1	Cont. 90 D1	Cont. 45 D1	Cont. 135 D1	Cont. 45 D1	Extent
Cont. STD D1	Entropy	Corr. 45 D1	Cont. 135 D1	Cont. 135 D1	Cont. Mean D1	Cont. 90 D1	Mean Intensity
Corr. STD D1 ²	Cont. 135 D1	Corr. 135 D1	Cont. Mean D1	Corr. 45 D1	Cont. STD D1	Cont. STD D1	Min Intensity
Cont. 0 D2	Cont. Mean D1	Corr. STD D1	Corr. 90 D1	Corr. 90 D1	Corr. STD D1	Corr. 45 D1	Max Intensity
Cont. 45 D2	Cont. STD D1	Homo. 45 D1	Cont. Mean D1	Corr. STD D1	Cont. 0 D2	Menopause	Skewness
Cont. 90 D2	Corr. STD D1	Homo. 135 D1	Corr. STD D1	Homo. 45 D1	Cont. 45 D2		Kurtosis
Cont. Mean D2	Energy 45 D1	Homo. Mean D1	Homo. 45 D1	Homo. 90 D1	Cont. 90 D2		Variance
Corr. 45 D2	Homo. 45 D1 ⁴	Cont. 90 D2	Homo. 90 D1	Homo. 135 D1	Corr. 90 D3		Cont. 90 D1
Corr. 90 D2	Homo. 135 D1	Corr. 0 D2	Homo. 135 D1	Cont. 45 D2	Corr. 0 D2		Cont. 135 D1
Corr. 135 D2	Homo. STD D1	Corr. 90 D2	Homo. Mean D1	Homo. 45 D2	Corr. 45 D2		Cont. 0 D2
Corr. Mean D2	Cont. 45 D2	Corr. 135 D2	Cont. 90 D2	Cont. 0 D3	Corr. 90 D2		Cont. 90 D2
Corr. STD D2	Corr. STD D2	Corr. Mean D2	Corr. 90 D2	Energy 45 D3	Corr. 135 D2		Cont. 45 D3
Cont. 90 D3	Corr. 90 D3	Homo. 90 D2	Homo. 135 D2	Height	Corr. Mean D2		Cont. 135 D3
Corr. 45 D3	Menarche	Cont. 45 D3	Circularity	Menarche	Corr. STD D2		Height
Corr. 90 D3	Menopause	Menopause	Compactness	Menopause	Cont. 0 D3		Menopause
Corr. Mean D3	Breast-feeding	PMH ⁵	Shape Ratio	PMH	Cont. 45 D3		No. of Pregn. ⁸

¹Cont.: Contrast ²Corr.: Correlation ³ED: Equivalent Diameter ⁴Homo.: Homogeneity ⁵PMH: Personal Medical History ⁶MaAL: Major Axis Length ⁷MiAL: Minor Axis Length ⁸No. of Pregn.: Number of Pregnancies

TABLE III

FEATURE RANKINGS FOR TUMOR GRADING (GRADE 2 VS. GRADE 3 CLASSIFICATION) USING VARIOUS SELECTION TECHNIQUES, WITH THE FINAL SELECTION HIGHLIGHTED IN BOLD.

t-test	MRMR	FI-ET	FI-RF	FI-XGB	SelectKBest	SFS	SBS
Cont. 0 D1 ¹	Euler Number	Orientation	Max Intensity	Extent	Kurtosis	Eccentricity	Area
Cont. 45 D1	Max Intensity	Solidity	Kurtosis	Mean Intensity	Cont. 0 D1	Mean Intensity	MiAL ⁷
Cont. 90 D1	Weight	Kurtosis	Cont. 0 D1	Min Intensity	Cont. 45 D1	Min Intensity	Convex Area
Cont. 135 D1	Height	Cont. 0 D1	Cont. 45 D1	Cont. 90 D1	Cont. 90 D1	Cont. 90 D1	Filled Area
Cont. Mean D1	Smoking	Cont. 45 D1	Cont. 90 D1	Cont. Mean D1	Cont. 135 D1	Corr. 90 D1	Perimeter
Cont. STD D1	AC ³	Cont. 90 D1	Cont. 135 D1	Homo. 0 D1	Cont. Mean D1	Corr. 90 D2	Max Intensity
Corr. STD D1 ²	Menarche	Cont. 135 D1	Cont. Mean D1	Homo. 90 D1	Corr. 90 D1	Height	Cont. 0 D1
Cont. 0 D2	Menopause	Corr. 90 D1	Corr. 0 D1	Corr. 45 D2	Corr. STD D1	Breast-feeding	Homo. 135 D1
Cont. 90 D2	Breast-feeding	Homo. 90 D1 ⁵	Corr. STD D1	Corr. Mean D2	Cont. 0 D2		Cont. 135 D2
Cont. 135 D2	PMH ⁴	Corr. Mean D2	Energy 135 D1	Homo. STD D2	Cont. 90 D2		Corr. 0 D2
Cont. Mean D2	Family history	Age	Energy STD D1	Cont. 45 D3	Cont. 135 D2		Homo. 0 D2
Cont. STD D2	Breast density	Weight	Homo. 90 D1	Corr. 90 D3	Corr. 90 D2		Homo. 90 D2
Corr. 90 D2		Height	Homo. 135 D1	Energy 90 D3	Corr. Mean D2		Homo. 135 D2
Corr. Mean D2		Menarche	Homo. 90 D2	Age	Cont. 90 D3		Cont. 90 D3
Corr. STD D2		Menopause	Corr. 90 D3	Weight	Corr. 90 D3		Corr. 0 D3
Cont. 90 D3		Breast-feeding	Corr. Mean D3	Menarche	Corr. Mean D3		Homo. 90 D3
Corr. 90 D3		No. of Pregn. ⁶	Shape Ratio	Menopause	Weight		Shape Ratio
Weight		PMH	Age	No. of Pregn.	Breast-feeding		Weight
Breast-feeding		Family history	Menopause	PMH	PMH		Height
Breast density		Breast density	No. of Pregn.	Breast density	Breast density		Menopause

¹Cont.: Contrast ²Corr.: Correlation ³AC: Alcohol Consumption ⁴PMH: Personal Medical History ⁵Homo.: Homogeneity ⁶No. of Pregn.: Number of Pregnancies ⁷MiAL: Minor Axis Length

(RBF kernel), and Extra Trees (ET), in a soft voting scheme. The highest performance was achieved with an ANN, which reached 82.5% sensitivity, 85.7% specificity, 84.4% accuracy, and an AUC of 0.84. The ANN architecture remained the same as in the previous task.

IV. DISCUSSION

The extensive feature selection process identified the most critical features for each classification task. For the *in situ* vs. invasive classification, most selected features were image-based, with only one epidemiological variable

contributing significantly. Conversely, for tumor grading, out of the 13 selected features, 7 were image-based, while the remaining 6 were epidemiological and medical history. This highlights the need for tailored feature selection approaches depending on the task.

For the classification of invasiveness, an ANN model achieved 88.3% accuracy, with high sensitivity (91.9%) and AUC (0.88), using LOPO CV. Notably, the model maintained a low False Positive rate per image (FPi) of 0.09 and a low False Negative rate per image (FNi) of 0.06, indicating a strong ability to correctly identify both classes.

Fig. 4. Results for the two classifications using different classifiers. *Inv*: *in situ* vs. invasive BC classification. *Grade*: Grade 2 vs. Grade 3 BC classification.

For tumor grading, the ANN achieved 84.4% accuracy, with balanced sensitivity (82.5%), specificity (85.7%), and an AUC of 0.84. The model demonstrated an F_{Pi} of 0.11 and an F_{Ni} of 0.09, showing a promising performance with balanced classification towards both classes. The low F_{Pi} and F_{Ni} values further support the clinical utility of the approach, suggesting that it can reduce unnecessary follow-up procedures while maintaining high diagnostic accuracy and reliability for both invasiveness classification and tumor grading.

Compared to prior studies in the literature, which often focused on simpler tasks such as benign vs. malignant classification, this study addresses the more clinically meaningful challenges of invasiveness classification and tumor grading using only standard mammography. This is the first study in which mammograms are used for the classification of BC type and grade, making direct comparison with other studies challenging. Differences in datasets, pre-processing methods, CV techniques, classifiers, and performance evaluation methodologies, further complicate such comparisons. However, the proposed method outperforms the two other studies available in the literature for *in situ* vs. invasive BC (88.3% vs. 84% in [12]) and tumor grading (0.84 vs. 0.76 AUC in [14]).

Some limitations of this study should be noted. First, the dataset is relatively small, comprising 58 patients, which may limit the generalizability of the findings across different populations and imaging systems. Data collection was further complicated by the need for confirmed histopathology results, epidemiological, and medical history data. Another limitation of this study is the aspect of potential differences in annotations when more experts evaluate the same mammograms, which has not been very rigorously evaluated yet.

Future work will focus on increasing the number of cases to include a more diverse and representative population, with a broader age range. Future studies will include separate training, validation, and external test sets to better assess the robustness of the proposed algorithm. When more data are available, new studies will be conducted to explore the use of DL and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents an algorithm for the automatic classification of breast cancer type (*in situ* vs. invasive) and tumor grading (grade 2 vs. grade 3) using standard mammographic images combined with epidemiological and medical history data. This is the only algorithm that takes into consideration digital mammograms for the classification of cancer type and tumor grade. Its results demonstrated robust performance, achieving high accuracy rates and outperforming other approaches presented in the literature. These promising results support the potential of non-invasive, image-based machine learning tools to assist radiologists in decision-making. By reducing unnecessary biopsies and enabling faster, more accurate assessment of tumor invasiveness and grade, such methods could enhance diagnostic efficiency and improve patient outcomes.

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